

ENGLISH PROVERBS

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The article deals with the languages of origin and sources of English proverbs. The aim of this study is to identify and quantify the rankings (based on the proportion of paremiological units) of languages of origin, personal, functional and stylistic and genre affiliation with textual sources of English proverbs. The study determines two main factors that affect the formation of the paremiological fund of the English language: the broad international and intercultural contacts (every third English proverb has foreign origin) and the writing tradition (almost half of the English proverbs goes back to written sources, different in terms of productivity and very diverse in functional and stylistic and genre affiliation). More over It finds out that English paremiological fund hasn't been subjected to significant influence of foreign languages in the new period (four out of five borrowed proverbs belong to classical languages and French, the influence of which was the most prominent on the English language in the ancient period and fully completed by the end of the middle period). The study also defines that the paremiological fund of the modern English possess a high proportion of the nationalcultural component (three out of the four authors of the English proverbs written sources turn out to be British or American).

Keywords: the English language, etymology, English paremiological fund, native English proverbs, borrowed proverbs in the English language, literary proverbs.

Introduction

Origin and sources of English proverbs are very diverse and are determined by the peculiarities of the historical dynamics of the English language, national specificity of British culture and the results of its contacts with other cultures in the world. According to its origin, English proverbs (as in any other European language) are traditionally divided into native and borrowed (mainly from Latin and French). The main sources of origin of English proverbs are well known: folklore, the Holy Scripture, literature (especially the works by William Shakespeare) (Zimovets, Matveeva, 2013: 27–29). However, a number of important questions remain unclear: the languages the proverbs were borrowed from, the texts that served as the sources of the proverbs, the functional, stylistic and genre variety of literary sources of proverbs, the authors who introduced many proverbs into English, etc.

The problem of distinguishing the etymological and functional approaches to determine the origin and source of proverbs wasn't solved. This fact creates very serious difficulties in description of English paremiological units, as well as their comparison with the proverbs of other languages, especially in the aspect of the opposition «national vs. universal», which is one of the most significant problems of today's paremiology. The aim of this study is to identify and quantify the rankings (based on the proportion of paremiological units) of languages of origin, personal, functional and stylistic and genre affiliation with textual sources of English proverbs. The actual data for study were 800 proverbs that are most commonly used in the modern English language, according to the explanatory dictionary «English Proverbs Explained» (1969) R. Rideout and C. Witting (Rideout, Witting, 1969).

1. Methodological bases of origin and sources of proverbs In determining the origin and textual sources of proverbs we strictly follow the etymological approach, taking into account that many modern native English speakers may not know who it belongs to or to what literary text the proverb originated from. However, basing on the knowledge of native speakers (functional approach) only, it is very difficult to characterize accurately the source of origin of the proverb. First, this knowledge differs significantly among different speakers, and second, to identify this knowledge it is required to hold the mass experiment, aimed to precise determination of the presence / absence in linguistic consciousness of the individual of the local association with the source of each proverb (author, text and so on), which is practically impossible. The exact origin of proverbs can't be always determined by special etymological analysis because of their predominantly verbal existence in speech, ancient origin of single proverbs and a number of productive proverb models and extralinguistic factors of paremiological borrowings. In this regard, the empirical material for the etymology of proverbs are mainly its written fixation, as well as the results of comparison of paremiological units of different languages and / or dialects.

It should be noted that the written fixation of a proverb cannot be the only sufficient basis to determine its origin and history. So, the proverb Call a spade a spade functions widely in modern English from the beginning of the twentieth century, according to R. Rideout and C. Witting, who refer to its use in the novel «The Card» (1911) by Arnold Bennett (Rideout, Witting, 1969: 67). It is possible to conclude that it has a relatively recent origin, especially as it occurs in the same form and the same meaning in the famous novel «The picture of Dorian Grey» (1890) by Oscar Wilde. However, this proverb was also used in the

commentary to the Bible «Mellificium theologicum, or the marrow of many good authors» (1647) by John Trapp (cf. : Gods people shall not spare to call a spade a spade, a niggard a niggard), so that this fact significantly increases the history of the proverb, but it also may indicate its literary origin, since it has not been previously recorded. Nevertheless, we can not say that Trapp was the first to use this proverb, that he didn't borrow it from an unknown text of another author, or borrowed it directly from the oral speech.

For example, we find a similar saying in the play «The Poetaster» (1601) by Ben Johnson: Ramp up my genius, be not retrograde; But boldly nominate a spade a spade (act 5, sc. 1). There is also a version according to which the origin of this proverb originates from classical Greek («Apophthegmata Laconica» by Plutarch, 178B). It was a mistaken translation of Ancient Greek phrase τὰ σῦκα σῦκα, τὴν σκάφην δὲ σκάφην ὀνομάσων ('calling figs figs, and a trough a trough') by the medieval scholar Desiderius Erasmus. He mistranslated the word σκάφη (skáphē - in English trough) as σκαφεῖον (skapheíon - in English digging tool). The phrase was introduced to English in 1542 in Nicolas Udall's translation of Erasmus "Apophthegmes, that is to saie, prompte sayynges. First gathered by Erasmus": Philippus answered, that the Macedonians wer feloes of no fyne witte in their termes but altogether grosse, clubbyshe, and rusticall, as they whiche had not the witte to calle a spade by any other name then a spade.

It is evident that the word spade refers to the instrument used to move earth, a very common tool. The same word was used in England, Denmark, and in the Netherlands, Erasmus' country of origin. If we look for it in the paremiological funds of other languages, it turns out that the model of "Call / call whom / what by their right names" (and converse model with the same semantics «Do not call / Do not call whom / what by their right names) is productive in proverbs of various European languages, including the Russian language, cf. : Fr. Appeler un chat un chat; Gr. Die Dinge beim rechten Namen nennen; Sp. Llamar al pan, pan y al vino, vino; Рус. Называть вещи своими именами, Зови / Называй белое белым / черное черным and so on. This paremiological model is not only international, but also has a very ancient origin (it was widely used in ancient China, ancient Greece in philosophical debates about the relationship of names and things). Thus, cross-language comparison proves folk, not literary origin of the proverb Call a spade a spade. When we were analysing contemporary English proverbs from the etymological point of view, we primarily relied on wide comparison of paremiological funds of European and a number of non-European languages (Permiakov, 1988: pp. 143-169; Gluski, 1971; Mieder,

1986; Strauss, 1994; Paczolay, 1997; Ley, 1998; Kotova, 2000; Ivanow, 2009) and we also used all available data on written fixation of proverbs (Browning, 1989; Knowles, 2009; Simpson, 1998). We chose the most ancient sources of proverbs (their written fixation) as an empirical basis for the identification and quantitative classification of their origin. In many cases, the history and etymology of modern English proverbs supplemented with new data.

2. The languages of origin of English proverbs The etymological analysis of the most common paremiological units of modern English established that there are 61.5 % native English proverbs of among them (including 2.5 % in American English) and 38.5 % borrowed from other languages. Borrowed proverbs can be differentiated into three groups – from classical European languages (26 %), from modern European languages (11.5 %), from non-European languages (0.5 %).

Of the two classical languages, the Latin language quantitatively dominated (20 % of the units), as it was the intermediate language of the majority of borrowings from the Greek language (6 %). Modern European languages as the origins of English proverbs can be divided into two nonequilibrium groups – Languages of the United Kingdom (2 %) and the languages of continental Europe (9.5 % units). The first group of languages includes Scottish (1.5 %) and Irish (0.5 %), the second – French (7 %), German (0.5 %), Spanish (0.5 %) and Italian (1, 5 %). Chinese and Persian (0.25 % and 0.25 % of the units respectively) belong to the group of non-European languages. The origin of a number of borrowed proverbs (0.5 %) could not be properly determined.

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